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12	coefficients following permutation testing with 1000 permutations.

13

14 **Figure S1. Relationships between abiotic factors and primary productivity.** Linear
 15 regressions were fitted to explore the relationship between climatic and edaphic factors and
 16 primary productivity across land use types (woodlands, grasslands, and croplands).
 17 Explained variation is expressed as R², and significance is indicated by asterisks (***, p-
 18 value < 0.001, **, p-value < 0.010, *, p-value < 0.050). Non-significant (p-value > 0.05)
 19 regressions are denoted with "n.s.". Shaded area indicates confidence interval (standard
 20 error).

21

22 **Figure S2. Relationships between microbial community metrics and primary productivity.**

23 Linear regressions (polynomial for community composition) were fitted to explore the

24 relationship microbial community metrics including total OTU richness, Shannon's diversity

25 index, and community composition (NMDS first dimension) with primary productivity across

26 land use types (woodlands, grasslands, and croplands). Explained variation is expressed as

27 R² (0-1), and significance is indicated by asterisks (***; p-value < 0.001, **; p-value < 0.010,

28 *; p-value < 0.050). Non-significant (p-value > 0.050) regressions are denoted with "n.s.".

29 Shaded area indicates confidence interval (standard error).

30

31 **Figure S3. Relationships between soil biodiversity and primary productivity.** Linear
 32 regressions were fitted to explore the relationship between the main bacterial and fungal
 33 phyla and primary productivity across land use types (woodlands, grasslands, and
 34 croplands). Linear regressions were also fitted to the relationship between primary
 35 productivity and the main functional groups (Bacterial chemoheterotrophs, N-fixing
 36 bacteria, mycorrhizal fungi, saprophytic fungi, and fungal plant pathogens). Explained
 37 variation is expressed as R², and significance is indicated by asterisks (***; p-value < 0.001,
 38 **, p-value < 0.010, *, p-value < 0.050). Non-significant (p-value > 0.05) regressions are
 39 denoted with "n.s.".

40

41 **Figure S4. Primary productivity across land use types.** Primary productivity data as obtained
 42 from Terra and Aqua satellites across land use types (woodlands; $n = 186$, grasslands; $n =$
 43 126 , croplands; $n = 277$). Grouping information (letters above boxplots) is provided as
 44 pairwise comparisons following Kruskal-Wallis (two-sided) rank test (different letters indicate
 45 significant difference at $p < 0.05$). Chi-squared (χ^2) provides an estimation of the overall
 46 difference among land use types, and degrees of freedom are indicated as “d.f”. Boxplots
 47 indicate median (middle line), 25th and 75th percentile (box), and minimum and maximum
 48 (whiskers). Boxplots also indicate outlier values.

		Variable selection		
		CROPLANDS	GRASSLANDS	WOODLANDS
		(n = 277)	(n = 126)	(n = 185)
<i>Climatic factors</i>	Precipitation	X	X	X
	Temperature	X	X	X
<i>Edaphic factors</i>	Clay content	X	X	X
	Sand content	X	X	
	Silt content			
	pH	X	X	X
	Microbial biomass	X	X	X
	Organic carbon	X	X	X
	Phosphorus content	X	X	X
	Nitrogen content			
	Bulk density	X	X	X
<i>Biodiversity (fungi)</i>	Total richness			
	Shannon's index			
	Community composition (NMDS1)			
	Basidiomycota	X	X	X
	Chytridiomycota	X	X	X
	Mucoromycota	X	X	X
	Ascomycota	X	X	X
	Mortierellomycota	X	X	X
<i>Biodiversity (bacteria)</i>	Total richness			
	Shannon's index			
	Community composition (NMDS1)			
	Acidobacteria	X	X	X
	Actinobacteria	X	X	
	Proteobacteria	X	X	
	Bacteroidetes	X		
	Nitrospirae		X	X
	Verrucomicrobia	X	X	X
	Firmicutes	X	X	X
<i>Biodiversity (functional groups)</i>	Bacterial chemoheterotrophs	X		
	Nitrogen-fixing bacteria	X	X	X
	Fungal saprotrophs			
	Fungal plant pathogens	X	X	X
	Mycorrhizal fungi	X	X	

49

50 Table S1. Variable selection for the cropland, grassland, and woodland dataset. A total of
51 34 explanatory variables were tested for collinearity after applying a threshold of ± 0.70
52 (Spearman's rank coefficient). Variables not selected with "X" were excluded before further
53 analyses because high multicollinearity was detected.

Variable	Reason	Reference
Nitrogen-fixing bacteria	N-fixing bacteria play a crucial role in converting atmospheric nitrogen into forms available to plants, thereby enhancing soil fertility and reducing the need for nitrogenous fertilizers	(Vitousek et al., 2013)
Mycorrhizal fungi	Mycorrhizal fungi form symbiotic relationships with most plants, aiding in nutrient uptake, particularly phosphorus, enhancing plant health, and improving soil structure.	(Gupta, 2020; van der Heijden et al., 2015)
Soil organic carbon	Soil organic carbon promotes water retention, supports microbial biodiversity, and acts as a sink for atmospheric CO ₂ .	(Weil & Magdoff, 2004)
Phosphorus content	Phosphorus is vital for plant energy transfer and contributes to microbial functions including organic matter decomposition	(Duncan et al., 2019)
Soil density	Soil density is a measure of soil compaction, and influences root penetration, water infiltration, and aeration. Lower density indicates good soil structure with sufficient pore spaces.	(Shah et al., 2017)
Microbial biomass	Microbial biomass represents the living part of soil organic matter and is a key indicator of microbial activity	(Zhou & Ding, 2007)
Pathogen richness	The richness of pathogenic taxa in a soil provides a measure of disease risk and potential loss in productivity	(Liu et al., 2022)

54 Table S2. Variables included in the soil health index.

55

	Croplands (n= 277)		Grasslands (n= 126)		Woodlands (n= 185)	
	R2	pval	R2	pval	R2	pval
N-fixing bacteria	0.04885	0.0001231	< 0.001	0.6728	< 0.001	0.6238
Mycorrhiza	< 0.001	0.3647	0.07007	0.001596	< 0.001	0.4875
Soil organic carbon	0.07084	4.21E-06	0.1316	1.78E-05	0.0646	0.0002827
Phosphorus content	0.05504	4.77E-05	0.03875	0.01537	0.003197	0.2089
Soil bulk density	< 0.001	0.4163	0.038	0.01624	0.00256	0.2266
Microbial biomass	< 0.001	0.4967	0.08228	0.0006607	0.05484	0.00078
Plant pathogens	0.0944	1.09E-07	0.03311	0.02324	< 0.001	0.987

56

57 **Table S3. Relationship between individual components of soil health and primary**
58 **productivity.** This table presents R-squared values (0-1) reflecting the strength of
59 association between each individual variable included in the index and primary productivity.
60 For the relationship between the soil health index and primary productivity, see Figure 2.

		Units	Croplands (n = 277)		Grasslands (n = 126)		Woodlands (n = 185)		Kruskal-Wallis test (Chi-squared)	Kruskal-Wallis test (p-value)	
<i>Climatic factors</i>	Precipitation	mm	48,54 ± 23,64	a	68,89 ± 28,57	b	64,07 ± 27,97	b	56,82	4,57E-13	
	Temperature	°C	17,3 ± 4,91	a	15,13 ± 3,5	b	14,44 ± 4,85	b	44,61	2,05E-10	
<i>Edaphic factors</i>	Clay content	(%)	23,31 ± 13,31	a	22,23 ± 11,35	a	14,73 ± 12,33	a	4,0034	0,1351	
	Sand content	(%)	35,41 ± 26	a	36,61 ± 20,97	a	47,72 ± 24,54	b	30,57	2,30E-07	
	Silt content	(%)	41,13 ± 19,43	a	40,86 ± 16,76	a	37,53 ± 17,27	a	3,97	0,137	
	pH	unitless	7,07 ± 1,02	a	6,29 ± 1,02	b	5,16 ± 1,12	c	222,42	< 2,2e-16	
	Microbial biomass	µg C/g soil	278,05 ± 156,11	a	455,45 ± 272,69	b	394,4 ± 335,85	c	44,53	2,14E-10	
	Organic carbon	g/Kg	18,61 ± 14,93	a	36,5 ± 33,8	b	59,23 ± 64,51	c	170,23	< 2,2e-16	
	Phosphorus content	mg/Kg	36,65 ± 30,45	a	22,81 ± 23,82	b	19,59 ± 21,41	b	60,48	1,21E-13	
	Nitrogen content	mg/Kg	1,82 ± 1,15	a	3,36 ± 2,54	b	3,25 ± 2,71	b	81,00	< 2,2e-16	
	Bulk density	g/cm ³	1,23 ± 0,2	a	1,06 ± 0,23	b	0,77 ± 0,36	c	202,79	< 2,2e-16	
	<i>Biodiversity (fungi)</i>	Total richness	OTU number	120,46 ± 26,67	a	129,48 ± 32,4	b	104,69 ± 30,2	c	57,91	2,66E-13
Shannon's index		unitless	3,86 ± 0,53	a	3,93 ± 0,64	a	3,48 ± 0,66	b	55,91	7,22E-13	
Community composition (NMDS1)		unitless	0,10 ± 0,07	a	0,03 ± 0,09	b	-0,16 ± 0,16	c	277,43	< 2,2e-16	
Basidiomycota		OTU number	17,34 ± 7,33	a	23,17 ± 10,94	b	33,23 ± 11,8	c	210,27	< 2,2e-16	
Chytridiomycota		OTU number	8,61 ± 4,61	a	7,8 ± 4,87	a	2,39 ± 3,27	b	222,66	< 2,2e-16	
Mucoromycota		OTU number	2,08 ± 1,97	a	3,72 ± 3,55	b	3,22 ± 3,06	b	30,47	2,42E-07	
Ascomycota		OTU number	71,69 ± 17,66	a	68,52 ± 23,64	a	51,94 ± 20,51	b	100,01	< 2,2e-16	
Mortierellomycota		OTU number	9,19 ± 4,02	a	9,4 ± 4,59	a	6,54 ± 4,84	b	58,42	2,06E-13	
<i>Biodiversity (bacteria)</i>		Total richness	OTU number	7417,12 ± 1122,83	a	6959,97 ± 1079,26	b	5797,98 ± 1648,39	c	111,54	< 2,2e-16
		Shannon's index	unitless	7,92 ± 0,3	a	7,75 ± 0,32	b	7,34 ± 0,52	c	164,98	< 2,2e-16
	Community composition (NMDS1)	unitless	-0,13 ± 0,14	a	-0,02 ± 0,15	b	0,21 ± 0,21	c	232,37	< 2,2e-16	
	Acidobacteria	OTU number	965,81 ± 251,36	a	1035,03 ± 230,47	b	1089,4 ± 210,19	c	30,44	2,45E-07	
	Actinobacteria	OTU number	1694,05 ± 328,01	a	1522,75 ± 428,15	b	1012,31 ± 561,86	c	154,85	< 2,2e-16	
	Proteobacteria	OTU number	2385,02 ± 426,75	a	2149,83 ± 402,81	b	1862,84 ± 587,83	c	102,79	< 2,2e-16	
	Bacteroidetes	OTU number	643,71 ± 214,04	a	529,41 ± 182,11	b	369,04 ± 228,53	c	138,8	< 2,2e-16	
	Nitrospirae	OTU number	19,6 ± 9,33	a	14,44 ± 9,73	b	6,27 ± 8,35	c	197,23	< 2,2e-16	
	Verrucomicrobia	OTU number	403,29 ± 134,63	a	441,89 ± 144,25	b	388,28 ± 126,25	a	11,95	0,002548	
	Firmicutes	OTU number	152,34 ± 81,8	a	118,16 ± 54,12	b	55,24 ± 47,4	c	228,84	< 2,2e-16	
<i>Biodiversity (functional)</i>	Bacterial chemoheterotrophs	OTU number	1676,78 ± 288,57	a	1339,74 ± 335,02	b	929,82 ± 472,29	c	246,99	< 2,2e-16	
	Nitrogen-fixing bacteria	OTU number	9,04 ± 4,68	a	9,87 ± 5,23	ab	9,94 ± 3,7	b	10,28	0,005849	
	Fungal saprotrophs	OTU number	71,44 ± 15,75	a	67,11 ± 19,95	a	50,41 ± 19,02	b	129,11	< 2,2e-16	
	Fungal plant pathogens	OTU number	11,01 ± 4,98	a	7,12 ± 4,81	b	1,55 ± 2,28	c	324,32	< 2,2e-16	
	Mycorrhizal fungi	OTU number	3,26 ± 4,52	a	6,61 ± 6,03	b	20,63 ± 12,05	c	286,89	< 2,2e-16	

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62 Table S4 Mean values of climatic and edaphic factors (\pm standard deviation) in soils from
63 cropland (n = 277), grassland (n = 126), and woodland (n = 185) sites used in this study.
64 Mean values of biodiversity measures are also shown for bacteria, fungi, and predicted
65 functional groups. Kruskal-Wallis test was used to assess the overall effect of land use type
66 on explanatory variables (chi-squared and p-value are indicated for each test). Grouping
67 information following pairwise Wilcoxon test is indicated for each test; different letters
68 indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

CROPLANDS		GRASSLANDS		WOODLANDS	
Variable	<i>p</i> -value	Variable	<i>p</i> -value	Variable	<i>p</i> -value
pH	0.0099	pH	0.0099	Temperature	0.0099
Acidobacteria	0.0099	Soil organic carbon	0.0099	Clay content	0.0297
Temperature	0.0099	Proteobacteria	0.0297	Soil organic carbon	0.0099
Firmicutes	0.0099	Microbial biomass	0.0594	pH	0.3168
Soil organic carbon	0.0099	Temperature	0.0594	Soil density	0.0297
Proteobacteria	0.0297	Basidiomycota	0.2970	Firmicutes	0.0297
Precipitation	0.0099	Precipitation	0.7525	Microbial biomass	0.0297
Actinobacteria	0.0099	Verrucomicrobia	0.3168	Precipitation	0.0297
Verrucomicrobia	0.2079	Mycorrhiza	0.0297	Verrucomicrobia	0.2772
Phosphorus content	0.0297	Acidobacteria	0.7525	Plant pathogens	0.6534

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71 Table S5 Exact *p*-values from each predictor in the Random Forest model based on the
72 averaged coefficients following permutation testing with 1000 permutations.

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